

COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF SMOKE TUNNEL FLOW VISUALIZATION: TECHNIQUES, EVOLUTION, AND TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATIONS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a comprehensive review of smoke tunnel flow visualization, focusing on the techniques, advancements, and technological innovations in the field. Smoke tunnels, a type of particle tracing method, are widely used to visualize airflow patterns around aerodynamic bodies, enabling insights into complex fluid dynamics. Key visualization methods discussed include particle image velocimetry, schlieren photography, and shadowgraph techniques. The paper also highlights design elements, such as honeycomb settling chambers and turbulence-reducing screens, essential for optimizing visualization accuracy. This review provides a valuable resource for understanding the evolution and future potential of flow visualization technology.

Keywords: Flow Visualization, Smoke Tunnel, Particle Tracing, Aerodynamic Bodies,

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I. INTRODUCTION

The process of making the physics of fluid flow visible is called flow visualization. Since the majority of fluids air, water, etc. are transparent, we cannot see their flow patterns unless we use specialized techniques [2]. There are three ways to see flows: optical methods, particle tracer methods, and surface flow visualization. When a solid surface is approached, surface flow visualization shows the flow streamlines in the limit. One example is when colored oil is sprayed to a wind tunnel model's surface; the oil reacts to the surface shear stress by forming a pattern. It is possible to trace the fluid velocity in a flow by adding particles, such as smoke [2]. These are shown using optical techniques called interferometry, schlieren photography, and the shadowgraph.

To see a portion of a complex fluid flow pattern, we can shine a sheet of laser light on the particles. Particle image velocimetry is a technique that allows us to see the flow and determine its velocity, provided that the particles faithfully follow the flow's streamlines. Lastly, variations in the optical refractive index of various flows show their patterns. The shadowgraph, schlieren photography, and interferometry are optical techniques used to visualize these [2]. For many years, fluid motion has been seen through the use of smoke. A particle tracing technique called Smoke Tunnel is used to visualize the air flow pattern to aerodynamic bodies [3]. A non-return or draft suction tunnel is the most widely used tunnel in flow visualization. As seen in Figure 1[2], air is sucked through a sizable settling chamber made up of a honeycomb and many screens, followed by a significant contraction, before entering the test section. The smoke can be expelled to the building's exterior based on this design. Honeycomb is used to disperse the massive air turbulence that enters the tunnel.

Several screens will be used to further lower the turbulence level prior to approaching the contraction phase. The screens ought to be positioned to minimize mesh size and provide the best possible outcome. The contraction section's purpose is to guarantee a consistent velocity profile at the test section's entry.

Figure 1 : Schematic of a Wind Tunnel [2]

II. HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE

Early Approaches (Pre-Industrial to Ancient) Simple techniques such as burning wood, leaves, and other organic materials were employed by early civilizations to produce smoke. This was frequently employed for simple investigations, religious rites, and signaling. In ancient combat, smoke was also employed for battlefield confusion and signaling [4]. **Production of Chemical Smoke (19th to Early 20th Century)** As chemistry advanced, more complex techniques for producing smoke were created. Smoke was produced for military training and battlefield use using mixtures such as sugar and potassium nitrate [5]. Smoke production became crucial for testing ventilation systems and other industrial uses as industries expanded. Although they were frequently toxic and dangerous, early synthesized compounds were occasionally used [6]. **Smoke from Oil (mid-20th century)** The use of mineral oil to create smoke in wind tunnels and other aerodynamic testing became commonplace around the middle of the 20th century [7].

In engineering applications, heating mineral oil creates a dense, observable smoke that is perfect for visualizing airflow [8]. Oil-based smoke was commonly used to create smoke screens for military operations and to test aircraft designs in wind tunnels [9].

Comprehensive Review of Smoke Tunnel Flow Visualization: Techniques, Evolution, and Technological Innovations

Smoke Based on Glycol (Late 20th Century) Glycol-based smoke, which is non-toxic and acceptable for indoor use, was used as a result of the entertainment industry's creation of fog machines [10]. These devices created a fine, smoke-like mist that was widely used in movie theaters, amusement parks, and other entertainment venues [11]. In emergency response and fire safety training, where safe yet realistic smoke conditions were required, glycol-based smoke was also used [12]. Contemporary Bio-Oils and Environmental Issues in the Twenty-First Century The use of bio-oils made from renewable resources for smoke production has gained attention due to growing environmental consciousness [13]. Compared to conventional mineral oils, these bio-oils are intended to be more environmentally friendly and have a smaller carbon impact [14]. Bio-oils are occasionally mixed with trace amounts of kerosene or other chemicals to enhance performance, striking a balance between the necessity for efficient smoke generation and environmental advantages [15]. These days, smoke oils are employed in many cutting-edge applications, ranging from live performances and virtual reality to accurate aerodynamic testing in smoke tunnels [16]. One of the best methods for enhancing our comprehension of intricate fluid flows in flow analysis is flow visualization [17]. According to Professor Brown of the University of Notre Dame, "A man is a man to see, and seeing, to analyze; he is not a dog to smell out each individual track." With the other senses serving as adjuncts, he is a sight tracker. Man is also a scanner, not just a spectator. Unless combined with other points that are somewhat better at other periods, a single point is meaningless. He need a broad perspective and the entire field [18]. As a result, numerous experiments have been conducted to support this claim. In 1883, Osborne Reynolds conducted an experiment that demonstrated the change from laminar to turbulent flow in a pipe using the dye injection method [19]. Because it was inexpensive and simple to use, the use of smoke and dye to observe fluid motion was one of the earliest visualization methods in fluid mechanics during Leonardo da Vinci's time [20]. To make it easier to investigate flow behavior in fluid mechanics, numerous investigations and analyses have also been conducted in the field of flow visualization [21]. Recent developments in physical modeling technology have made it easier to visualize flow to enhance study, according to Kerenyi (1999) [22]. The hydrogen bubble technique, which involves mounting a platinum wire vertically upstream of a bridge construction in the test flume, is now used to visualize flow [23]. The anode is a rod of graphite. Within the visibility area, the buoyancy of the hydrogen bubbles generated can be disregarded due to their small size [24]. The phase speed of the dive current created at the structure face can be visualized by using pulsed time-lime markers with a specially designed hydrogen bubble generator [25]. Bridge scour is typically caused by the plunging current. Therefore, the hydrogen bubble technique for flow visualization offers a better understanding of the flow patterns brought on by barriers [26]. Additionally, it can shorten trial duration to achieve favorable outcomes and provides prompt feedback for flow modification ideas [27]. Fichtelman (2001) asserts that the performance of sports balls, including knuckleballs, cricket balls, tennis balls, and golf balls, is greatly impacted by the concepts of fluid dynamics, including lift and drag forces [28]. This has been demonstrated through the use of smoke flow visualization studies to identify flow separation locations associated with sports ball surface characteristics [29]. During testing, a number of aerodynamic concepts were also used, including the use of a Jet Stream Wind Tunnel (Ref 1) to quantify lift and drag [30]. The side and lift forces produced by sports balls as a result of their surface characteristics were explained by Bernoulli's theorem [31]. The formation and behavior of the boundary layer on the surface of sports balls have a significant impact on their aerodynamics [32]. The speed at which flow becomes turbulent is known as the critical Reynolds number, and it falls as surface roughness increases [33]. Dry ice was used for wind visualization investigations [34].

A hose and soda straws were used to connect a cooler filled with dry ice to the Jet Stream wind tunnel's air intake chamber [35]. Two horizontal rows were made with six straws [36]. For photography, this was utilized to align and focus the smoke [37].

Goggles and thick gloves were used to lay dry ice in a two-and-a-half-gallon cooler. To produce smoke, hot water was applied to the dry ice [38]. The only light source was a tiny fluorescent strip above the test chamber, and a copper funnel covered the cooler and was attached to the straws via a plastic tube [39]. Every sports ball's performance is determined by Newtonian physics and fluid dynamics. Sports balls' surface characteristics have an impact on lift drag, boundary layer separation, and flight pattern [40]. Individual sports can be made more enjoyable by improving sports ball performance through an awareness of these principles [41]. Airflow in electrical systems was visualized by Azar & Rodgers (2001). Flow visualization can help clear up a lot of misunderstandings about fluid flow behavior and is also a reasonable way to start researching a novel flow scenario [42]. Examining how heat dissipation is influenced by convective heat transfer is essential to comprehending this process in electronic devices [43]. However, one must take into account that laminar, transitional, and turbulent flows require a different visualization method in order to employ the best strategy for a particular situation [44]. As a result, there are two types of flow visualization techniques: 1) those that are appropriate for examining the intricacy of the streamline immediately above a surface, and 2) those that are appropriate for describing the characteristics of surface heat transfer [45]. A thorough explanation of flow phenomena and how they impact heat transfer processes can be obtained by combining the various analyses. Large amounts of smoke are utilized in the smoke-tube approach to create a small number of fairly thick streaks. On the other hand, very thin smoke streaks can be produced using the smoke-wire approach [46]. Consequently, methods for visualizing flow that are relevant to airflow in electronic systems [47]. Flow visualization, according to W.J. Devenport & W. L. Hartwell (2006), is an experimental method of analyzing the flow pattern across a body's surface or around it [48]. By adding dye, smoke, or pigment to the flow in the study region, the flow can be seen [49]. By using biofuel flow visualization.

III. METHODOLOGY AND MATERIALS REQUIRED

Goals and Design Specifications: It's crucial to establish the goals and purpose of a smoke tunnel before starting construction. This involves knowing the precise kind of flow visualization you want to do, be it studying flow patterns over objects, assessing aerodynamic properties, or just watching fluid behavior in a controlled setting. Establishing specific goals will aid in the improvement of other design elements, such as the tunnel's dimensions, which must take into account the size of the objects being tested while yet providing enough room for observation. The tunnel's design and component selection will be influenced by the intended airflow speed, homogeneity, and stability, therefore flow characteristics are also very important. Lastly, choosing the right biofuel is essential because it should consistently emit non-toxic smoke that doesn't jeopardize safety or air quality. For these uses, ethanol and biodiesel are frequently good options because they emit clear, visible smoke.

Conceptual Smoke Tunnel Design: The foundation of a working smoke tunnel is the conceptual design. The main structure of the tunnel can be either rectangular or cylindrical, depending on the visual clarity and desired airflow characteristics. An air intake section's primary function is to pull in and steady the airflow, typically accomplished by installing a fan at the entrance. Before the air reaches the test room, it passes through a settling chamber, which usually has screens or honeycomb structures to eliminate turbulence and create a smooth, laminar flow. A contraction portion follows, during which the tunnel narrows and the airflow is accelerated to the required speed while remaining uniform.

Comprehensive Review of Smoke Tunnel Flow Visualization: Techniques, Evolution, and Technological Innovations

The main testing area needs to be able to accommodate things of interest, including models of wings or other structures, and be transparent for convenient inspection. In order to prevent backflow and to maintain a constant, even flow in the test section, a diffuser is lastly added at the exit to progressively slow down the airflow. Together, these elements provide the required clarity of visualization and flow quality.

System for Creating and Injecting Biofuel Smoke: To visualize the tunnel's flow patterns, an efficient smoke generation system is essential. This concept produces biofuel smoke by vaporizing ethanol, frequently with the use of a controlled burner or heated chamber that emits a continuous stream of smoke. In order to guarantee a uniform flow and avoid interfering with the airflow itself, this smoke source needs to be placed carefully. The smoke is delivered steadily by the injection mechanism, which is usually a pump or vaporizer, and is precisely directed into the test area by fine tubes or needles. To prevent disrupting the flow, these tubes should be positioned at the start of the test chamber and gently inject the smoke into the airstream. To reduce the chance of unintentional igniting or overheating, make sure the system is well-ventilated, has temperature control features, and is made of fire-resistant materials.

Tunnel and Component Fabrication: The conceptual design becomes tangible at the fabrication stage. The tunnel walls' structural integrity is maintained while visibility is guaranteed by the use of transparent, long-lasting materials like tempered glass or acrylic. Metal frames and structural elements can be used to give the necessary support, especially for areas that house the smoke generator or fan. For airflow management, a high-quality fan with adjustable speeds is necessary. It should be installed firmly to prevent vibrations that could obstruct flow visibility. Careful sealing is necessary throughout the assembly of the diffuser, test section, and settling chamber to avoid air leaks that can impede airflow. In order to accomplish smooth smoke distribution and effectively remove any remaining smoke from the tunnel, preventing clouding in the visualization region, great attention must also be paid to the installation of the smoke injection system and exhaust.

Calibration and Testing: Thorough testing and calibration are essential when the tunnel is put together to make sure it functions as planned. Setting the fan speed and making sure the smoke distribution is consistent throughout the test section are the first steps in testing the airflow. In order to confirm this and help adjust the system, flow measurement tools such as anemometers can be employed to track the rate and consistency of airflow. At this point, smoke visibility should also be evaluated to make sure it is sufficient for collecting distinct flow patterns. A consistent, visible smoke line can be achieved by moving smoke outlets or altering the smoke injection rate, if necessary. Standardized objects, such as spheres or airfoils, can be placed within the test chamber to confirm that the tunnel can accurately visualize laminar flow and to make sure the configuration is adjusted for reliable outcomes.

Considering Safety and the Environment: Using biofuel in a smoke tunnel requires both environmental responsibility and safety. Since restricted smoke can deteriorate air quality and increase the risk of fire, adequate ventilation is required to prevent the buildup of biofuel vapors. Using flame-resistant materials for any portion that may be exposed to high temperatures or sparks is advised because fire safety precautions are also very important. Safety procedures and fire extinguishers must to be present at all times. While safely storing the fuel helps prevent environmental damage, managing biofuel correctly reduces hazards and guarantees efficiency.

Reducing emissions and preserving resources can also be achieved by limiting gasoline consumption.

Maintenance and Operation: To keep the smoke tunnel safe and functional, it needs to be maintained on a regular basis. Routine cleaning helps maintain sight and flow quality because biofuel smoke residue can build up on the tunnel walls and other parts over time.

To find any wear or possible leaks that can affect airflow and vision, the fan, smoke generator, and structural elements must undergo routine system inspections. Keeping track of calibration information, biofuel use, and operating parameters will help with future testing and provide steady performance over time. The longevity and dependability of the smoke tunnel setup are increased by this record-keeping, which also acts as a useful guide for any necessary modifications or repairs.

This thorough method of planning, constructing, and sustaining a smoke tunnel for biofuel-based flow visualization ought to contribute to the achievement of dependable, transparent outcomes while abiding by safety and environmental regulations.

1. **Frame & Housing** - a sturdy metal frame that stabilizes and supports the entire tunnel structure, guaranteeing that every component is attached securely.

Figure 2: Frame and Housing

2. **Tunnel Body** - A transparent enclosure that forms the main airflow path and makes it possible to clearly see the smoke patterns in the test area is usually made of acrylic or polycarbonate.

Figure 3: Tunnel Body

3. **Fan & Flow Control** - Controlled airflow is produced by an axial or centrifugal fan, and laminar flow is maintained for easy viewing in the test area using flow straighteners like honeycomb grids.

Comprehensive Review of Smoke Tunnel Flow Visualization: Techniques, Evolution, and Technological Innovations

Figure 4: Fan and Flow Control

- 4. Smoke Generation System** - Visible smoke is produced by a biofuel reservoir and a heated nozzle or wick, making it possible to see the tunnel's airflow clearly. (Based on Biofuel)

Figure 5: Smoke Generation System

- 5. Improvements of Visualization** - Smoke visibility is improved by LED lighting systems positioned along the tunnel; colorful gels are optionally used to draw attention to particular airflow areas.

Figure 6: Improvements of Visualization

- 6. Instruments for Measurements and Control** - Anemometers and thermocouples are examples of devices that detect temperature and airflow speed, allowing for accurate control and observation of experimental conditions.

IV. TECHNOLOGICAL ADVANCEMENTS

We use new technology that has been not implemented at any of the smoke generator because our smoke tunnel will be operated or controlled by using remote system and we are going to use the non toxic human friendly chemical like fog oil which can be made by vegetable waste.

V. COMPARATIVE STUDY

The goal of a comparative study on smoke tunnel design and fabrication is to examine different ways for building these flow visualization tools, with a focus on elements like tunnel geometry, material selection, and smoke generation techniques. The study assesses the effectiveness of smoke injection systems, such as oil-based foggers or vaporized fluid systems, and analyzes various manufacturing techniques, such as the usage of acrylic, aluminum, and stainless steel for durability.

Providing efficient sealing to prevent leaks, adjusting lighting for distinct smoke patterns, and guaranteeing consistent airflow through honeycombs or screens are important design factors. In order to determine the most efficient and useful smoke tunnel configurations for particular applications, such as fluid dynamics and aerodynamics research, the study also evaluates the cost, complexity, and overall performance of various designs by examining elements like flow clarity, ease of operation, and maintenance requirements.

VI. CONCLUSION

Smoke can be used as a kind of particle tracer to explore and comprehend fluid mechanics flow research. This allows for the observation of fluid behavior. This experiment will be carried out efficiently and simply using an air blower portion, diffuser, contraction cone, settling chamber, and transparency test section make up this portable smoke tunnel. It will therefore improvise and use a range of flow visualization techniques.

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